

Light-scattering Studies in Solutions of Gum Arabic

S. N. Mukherjee and S. K. Deb

Light-scattering measurements of gum arabic have been made in aqueous solution, in 0.02*N*-KCl solution, and in a mixture of 0.02*N* each of K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ chloride solution. The molecular weight of the gum after proper correction records a value of 0.58×10^6 . The molecular size, i.e., the root-mean-square end-to-end distance of the polymeric coil is 240 m μ in aqueous solution. This is reduced to 109m μ in 0.02*N*-KCl and 113m μ in a mixture of 0.02*N*-KCl, CaCl₂, and MgCl₂ solutions. These results indicate that a high contraction of the gum molecule takes place in presence of gegen ions.

The study of large molecules in solution by means of light scattering¹⁻³ has been one of the great developments in Chemistry during the last few years. It offers a better scope in the determination of molecular weight and dimension of macromolecules than the other known methods. This technique has been utilised in this investigation to study the molecular weight and size of various natural gums. The results embodied in this communication have been obtained from measurements on gum arabic, a complex polysaccharide of the random coiled type⁴ which exists as a neutral or slightly acid salt containing calcium, magnesium, and potassium cations.

A considerable amount of work has been done on the polysaccharide acid of gum arabic, i.e., arabic acid, by Veiss and Eggenberger⁴ who prepared the acid by removal of the cations on treatment with hydrochloric acid. The molecular weight of arabic acid was found by them to be 1.0×10^6 . The molecular dimension in aqueous solution of arabic acid after complete neutralisation with sodium hydroxide exhibited a value of 240 m μ in comparison with 105 m μ in dimension when the acid was dissolved in 0.02*N*-HCl. It appears from their results that arabic acid molecule becomes highly extended on ionisation, but if the ionisation is suppressed by addition of acid, the molecule tends to contract appreciably.

To ascertain the validity of the results obtained by Veiss and Eggenberger⁴ for arabic acid with respect to the whole gum, the following investigation on gum arabic has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sample of gum arabic was obtained from Stafford Allen and Sons Ltd., England. It was purified by repeated (three times) precipitation from aqueous solution with ethanol.

1. Stein and Doty, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 159.
2. Halwer *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1951, 73, 2786.
3. Doty and Bunce, *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 5029.
4. *Ibid.*, 1954, 76, 1, 560.

The precipitated product was washed several times with absolute ethanol followed by dry ether, the last traces of the ether having been removed on exposure to dry air at 30°. Weighed quantity of the purified gum was dissolved in distilled water in 0.02*N*-KCl, and in a mixture containing 0.02*N* each of KCl, CaCl₂, and MgCl₂ solution. The potassium chloride used was of extra pure quality (E. Merck); the other chlorides were freshly prepared from the corresponding calcium and magnesium carbonates (E. Merck) on addition of requisite quantities of HCl.

The solvents and solutions of gum arabic were made dust-free by repeated filtration through sintered glass funnels. Light-scattering measurements were made at 45°, 90°, and 135° in a Brice-Phoenix Light Scattering Photometer (Phoenix Precision Instrument Co.) using a semi-octagonal dissymmetry cell (40 × 40 × 120 mm). The wave length of light used was 436 mμ.

Turbidity was calculated by measuring scattering ratio, i.e., the ratio of light scattered by the solution at 90° (with no neutral filter in the primary beam) to the light transmitted at 0° (with neutral filter or filters of accurately known transmittance), the two quantities being recorded in terms of galvanometric deflection. Turbidity of the solvent was also determined and it was subtracted from each of the solutions. The dissymmetry (*z*) was calculated from the ratio of galvanometric deflection at 45° to that at 135°, the deflection of the solvent being subtracted from that of each of the solutions. These experiments were repeated for other concentrations of the solution.

The specific refractive increments, $(n - n_0)/c$, were determined at 436 mμ with a Brice-Phoenix Differential Refractometer (Phoenix Precision Instrument Co.).

DISCUSSION

The molecular weight, *M*, was calculated from the experimentally determined ~~value~~ of turbidity, *T* (cm⁻¹), the two quantities being related according to the Debye equation⁵:

$$Hc/TP_{90}^{\circ} = \frac{1}{M} + 2BcP_{90}^{\circ} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where *c* is the concentration in g./ml, *B* is a constant, and *P*₉₀[°] is the particle scattering factor at 90°. The quantity *H* is equal to

$$32 \pi^3 n_0^2 [(n - n_0)/c]^2 / 3N \lambda^4$$

where *n*₀ is the refractive index of the solvent and *n*, that of the solution; λ is the wave length of light used and *N* is the Avogadro number.

The intercept of the plot of *Hc/T* with *c* (equation 1) is the reciprocal of the weight average molecular weight uncorrected for any interference effect. To obtain the correct molecular weight, this quantity is to be multiplied with the reciprocal of the particle scattering factor *P*₉₀[°]. This factor is related to the intrinsic dissymmetry (*z*) extrapolated to infinite dilution. Knowing the reciprocal particle-scattering factor from the intrinsic

dissymmetry, the value of the root-mean-square end-to-end distance can be calculated by using the theoretical curves⁶ with the assumption in this case of a polydisperse random coil as the suitable model⁴.

The values of Hc/T with c and those of z with c are separately plotted in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

FIG. 1 Variation of Hc/T with conc. of gum arabic.

- (1) In water.
 - (2) In 0.02N-KCl.
 - (3) In 0.02N-KCl + CaCl₂ + MgCl₂.
- $H = 0.6172 \times 10^{-5}$.

FIG. 2. Variation of dissymmetry with conc. of gum arabic.

- (1) In water.
- (2) In 0.02 N-KCl.
- (3) In 0.02 N-KCl + CaCl₂ + MgCl₂.

The plot of Hc/T with c (Fig. 1) for gum arabic in aqueous solution exhibits a typical polyelectrolytic behaviour, the curvature making the extrapolation uncertain, resulting in an inaccurate determination of the molecular weight. It has been observed by Katochalsky and Eissenberg⁷ that the molecular weight of polymethacrylic acid can be accurately obtained by complete repression of ionisation by using 0.02N-HCl as a solvent when the plot becomes linear, rendering extrapolation easy and accurate. Trap and Hermans⁸, working with sodium methoxycarbonyl cellulose obtained an almost linear graph on using 0.05N-NaCl as a solvent for the macromolecule. Veiss and Eggenberger⁴ achieved the same result for arabic acid when the scattering measurements were made in 0.02N-HCl.

It appears that a linear plot of Hc/T with c can be expected for gum arabic if sufficient amount of K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ ions be added to neutralise the effect of charges of the macro-ion. To this end, the scattering measurements were made in 0.02N-KCl and in a mixture of 0.02N solution each of KCl, CaCl₂, and MgCl₂. A linear graph resulted in both the cases, but the slopes differed considerably. The graph for the mixture showed smaller slope and was almost parallel to the abscissa (curve 3, Fig. 1).

The dissymmetry values (Fig. 2) of the gum in both aqueous and KCl solutions exhibited an increase at a very high dilution; this effect, however, was not prominent in

6. Doty and Steiner, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, 28, 1, 211.

7. *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1951, 6, 767.

8. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 757.

the solution containing mixed K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} ions. The rise in the value for gum arabic at a very high dilution may be attributed to the presence of either dust or to high ionisation. The z values in these two cases were calculated after neglecting the higher values at the most dilute solutions. The value of z in the aqueous solution also appeared to be much higher than those obtained from measurements in the KCl solution alone and in the solution containing the other cations together. The interpretation of these results will be discussed later. The intrinsic dissymmetry (z) of gum arabic in presence of 0.02N-KCl, 0.02N-CaCl₂, and 0.02N-MgCl₂ has been calculated for the molecular weight correction factor. The molecular weight, M , of gum arabic after this correction is found to be 0.58×10^6 . This value is considerably higher than that determined by osmotic pressure measurements⁹ (0.24×10^6). The fluorescence and depolarisation correction have been made by the usual procedure, but their influence being negligible, the molecular weight is expected to remain unaltered. A reasonable explanation of this behaviour can be attempted if the system is polydisperse and a relatively small number of large particles present is likely to contribute a great deal to light scattering, whereas in the osmotic pressure determination these large particles remain almost inactive.

On comparing the molecular weight of gum arabic, as determined here, with that of arabic acid by Veiss and Eggenberger⁴, it is evident that although the value of gum arabic is considerably lower than that of arabic acid, the two are of the same order. This discrepancy can be accounted for in terms of unequal distribution of polydispersity in either of these two materials. In the arabic acid, the larger particles are possibly more predominant than in gum arabic.

It appears (Fig. 2) that the intrinsic dissymmetry of gum arabic is 2.84 in aqueous solution, 1.56 in 0.02N-KCl, and 1.62 in 0.02N K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} chloride solution, which refers to a root-mean-square end-to-end distance of the polymeric coil as 240 m μ , 109 m μ , and 113 m μ respectively.

These molecular dimensions of gum arabic are comparable to those obtained for arabic acid when the polymer is made to ionise completely by neutralisation with NaOH and also when the ionisation is completely suppressed by addition of a common ion in the form of 0.02N-HCl. The low values of the molecular dimension of the gum, determined from measurements in the salt solution, indicates that a high contraction in the size of the gum takes place in presence of the gegen ions. It is clear that in aqueous solution, there being no ions added from outside, the charged groups of the ionised molecule exhibit repulsion and as a result, the molecule undergoes expansion. In presence of salts, the gegen ions present screen the charged groups and repulsion between them becomes less; under these conditions the molecule undergoes contraction.

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